

**INTERACTIVE METHODS AND THEIR IMPORTANT ROLE IN
TEACHING STUDENTS**
**ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И ИХ ЗНАЧИТЕЛЬНАЯ РОЛЬ В
ОБУЧЕНИИ УЧЕНИКОВ**

Жолдасбаева Малика

Студентка 4 курса НГПИ имени Ажинияза

Abstract: The article discusses interactive methods and their use by teachers in the classroom, as well as the interaction of teachers with students during the lesson

Key words: interactive method, the joint activity, the passive method, the active method

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются интерактивные методы и их использование учителями на уроке, а также взаимодействие учителей с учащимися во время урока

Ключевые слова: интерактивный метод, совместная деятельность, пассивный метод, активный метод

Annotatsiya: maqolada interaktiv metodlar va o'qituvchilar tomonidan darsda foydalanish, shuningdek, dars davomida o'qituvchilar va talabalar o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlar ko'rib chiqiladi

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv usul, qo'shma faoliyat, passiv usul, faol usul

Currently, the approach to learning should focus on introducing novelty and innovation into the learning process, due to the peculiarities of the dynamics of the development of life and activity, the specifics of various learning technologies and the needs of the individual, society and the state in developing socially useful knowledge, beliefs, traits and qualities of character, attitudes and behavioral experience in students [1].

The main methodological innovations are connected today with the use of interactive teaching methods. The word "interactive" came to us from English from the word "interact". "Inter" – "mutual", "act" – to act. The interactive method means interaction, being in the mode of conversation, dialogue. This means that interactive methods are focused on the broad interaction of the student not only with the teacher, but also with each other in the learning process. These methods are most consistent with a personality-oriented approach to learning. They involve co-learning, and both the student and the teacher are subjects of the educational process. The teacher often acts only as the organizer of the learning process, the leader of the group, the creator of conditions for the initiative of students [3].

Thus, interactive learning consists in the fact that the learning process is organized in such a way that almost all students are involved in the process of cognition, they have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think. The joint activity of students in the process of learning, mastering the educational material means that everyone makes their own special individual contribution, there is an exchange of knowledge, ideas, ways of activity. Moreover, this happens in a good atmosphere of goodwill and mutual support, which allows not only to gain new knowledge, but also develops cognitive activity itself. When using interactive methods, students [1]:

- the interest in the learning process, the assimilation of the material rises;
- feedback is being provided;
- opinions and views are formed;
- life skills.

The passive method is a form of interaction between students and the teacher, in which the teacher is the main actor and controls the course of the lesson, and students act as passive listeners, subject to the directives of the teacher. The teacher's communication with students in passive lessons is carried out through surveys in the classroom, independent, control works, tests, etc.

The active method is a form of student–teacher interaction in which the teacher and students interact with each other during the lesson. The students here are not passive listeners, but active participants in the lesson. If in the passive lesson the main actor and the lesson manager was the teacher, then here the teacher and the students are on equal rights. If passive methods assumed an authoritarian style of interaction, then active methods assume a democratic style more. Many people put an equal sign between active and interactive methods, however, despite the commonality, they have differences. The interactive method means to interact, to be in a conversation mode, a dialogue with someone. In other words, unlike active methods, interactive methods are focused on broader interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and on the dominance of student activity in the learning process.

The teacher's place in interactive lessons is reduced to the direction of students' activities to achieve the lesson goals. The teacher also develops a lesson plan (usually interactive exercises and tasks, during which the student learns the material).

The main components of interactive lessons in the educational process are interactive exercises and tasks that are performed by students. A significant difference between interactive exercises and tasks from the usual ones is that by performing them, the student not only and not so much consolidate the already studied material, as they study a new one [2].

In addition to the methods presented, the most popular methods are used in modern literature, such as:

- creative tasks;
- work in small groups;
- educational (role–playing and business games);
- use of public resources (invited specialists, excursions);
- study and consolidation of new material (interactive lecture, work with visual aids, video and audio materials, "student as a teacher", "everyone teaches everyone", etc.);
- discussion of complex and discussion issues and problems;
- problem solving (Pattern method, "Decision tree", etc.);
- "Brainstorming".

The use of these methods allows students to develop logic in making various decisions, as well as to see a perspective in a particular situation or task.

Thus, it can be concluded that it is advisable for a teacher to combine various methods and technologies of interactive learning, which will achieve the greatest effect from their application. The interactive methods discussed above can be applied when teaching various subjects in the educational process.

References:

1. Interactive teaching methods [Electronic resource]. Access mode: [http://nsportal.ru/nachalnayashkola/materialy-o/2013/12/21/interativnye -...](http://nsportal.ru/nachalnayashkola/materialy-o/2013/12/21/interativnye-...)
2. Interactive teaching methods and their classification [Electronic resource]. Access mode: http://www.rusnauka.com/16_NPRT_2013/Pedagogica/5_138923.doc.htm
3. Solovyova Yu.Yu. The use of interactive teaching methods in the formation of professional qualities of a manager: integration of the educational space with the real sector of the economy H 3: collection of materials of the International Scientific and Methodological Conference, February 27, March 2, 2012, Novosibirsk. – Novosibirsk: SGGA, 2012.-277 p.

